

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL NEEDS OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the issues of developing the professional training of future technological education teachers from a socio-pedagogical point of view. The rapid pace of technological development, the implementation of modern approaches in education, and the need to form innovative thinking in students increase the requirements for technological education teachers. Therefore, improving the professional training of teachers, taking into account digital technologies in the pedagogical process, modern requirements of the labor market, and the social needs of society, is considered one of the urgent tasks.

Keywords: technological education, professional training, socio-pedagogical necessity, innovative approach, professional competence, digital technologies.

Introduction.

In modern society, technological progress is deeply penetrating into every aspect of our lives. Today, as the foundation of any socio-economic development, the education of young people with technical thinking, striving for innovation, and creative thinking is emerging as an urgent task. In particular, the field of technological education, with its unique characteristics, prepares the future generation for the world of modern technology and technology. Such a process, first of all, is directly dependent on the level of professional training and professional competencies of educators working in this area of education. The future teacher of technological education is considered not only a person who gives knowledge, but also directs the student to practical activities, forms innovative thinking. Therefore, the need for a social and pedagogical approach to the issue of their professional training is on the agenda. Because a teacher of technological education is required to be armed with modern technical means, digital technologies, production processes and scientific and technical innovations, and at the same time, to have pedagogical skills, adapted to social activity, and personal maturity. Therefore, the development of professional training of future teachers of technological education remains one of the important criteria for the development of not only the education system, but also the entire society. This article analyzes the socio-pedagogical necessity of this process, its structural aspects, problems and prospects.

In today's educational process, the need for teachers in the technological direction is significantly increasing. Because the training of qualified specialists in areas related to industry, production and modern technologies begins precisely at the school level. The professional training of future teachers of technological education directly affects not only the quality of education, but also the level of technical thinking of the younger generation. Technological education, by its very nature, requires a combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Therefore, higher educational institutions that train pedagogical personnel require a modern and comprehensive approach to the professional training of

future teachers. They should be mature enough to teach not only to teach, but also to teach students creativity, independent thinking, and problem-solving.

Professional training is not only a set of knowledge, but also includes socio-pedagogical competencies, communicative potential, effective use of information technologies, and mastery of modern teaching methods. Especially since today, technologies such as digitization, STEM approach, robotics, 3D-modeling are increasingly used in education, the training of future teachers in these areas is necessary.

From a socio-pedagogical point of view, the personal qualities of a technological education teacher are also of great importance - responsibility, initiative, ability to work in a team, ability to establish psychological dialogue with a student. It is impossible to overestimate the social role of a teacher in arousing students' interest in technology, guiding them towards a profession, and realizing their talents. Therefore, in the system of training teachers of technological education, integrated approaches, educational and practical training, internships in cooperation with production, and innovative methodologies are of great importance. After all, a modern teacher is not only a provider of knowledge, but also a coach, mentor, and motivator who prepares students for real life.

Literature analysis (review):

The analysis of scientific and methodological sources on the professional training of future teachers of technological education shows the relevance of this area and the need for extensive research. The literature on this topic mainly covers issues of modern pedagogical approaches, innovative educational technologies, organization of education based on competencies, and improvement of professional training.

In particular, the resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education (for example, Resolution No. PQ-2909, 2017) emphasize the need for modern approaches to teacher training, professional qualifications, and thorough mastery of information and communication technologies. These documents provide for the modernization of the technological education sector based on the requirements of the time.

The works of prominent scientists in the field of pedagogy A. A. Kiryakova, V. A. Slastenin, N. D. Nikandrov systematically covered the personal and professional formation of future teachers. Their scientific research deeply revealed the psychological, didactic and methodological foundations of professional training.

The works of local researchers, pedagogical scientists of Uzbekistan - M. Kurbonov, Z. Abdukarimova, G. Yuldoshev, indicate the harmony of education and upbringing, the development of a creative approach and technological thinking as important factors in the formation of professional competence of future teachers.

Also, foreign literature (P. Drucker, J. Dewey, K. Robinson) widely covers the issues of organizing technological education, interactive teaching methods, modern pedagogical design and the use of digital tools. These sources serve as an important theoretical basis for understanding the ways of developing the competencies of future teachers in accordance with the requirements of modern society. The analysis of the above literature shows that the professional training of future teachers of technological education is a multifactorial, complex area that requires an integrated approach and should be considered in the integral unity of pedagogical, psychological, social and technological approaches.

Discussion:

One of the most important tasks facing the modern education system is the formation of qualified specialists who can train a new generation of teachers, especially in the technological direction. In this process, not only the level of knowledge of the future teacher in the subject, but also his personal qualities, social activity, communicative culture and pedagogical skills come into play as one of the main factors. During the discussion, it should be noted that today the teacher of technological education is required not only to conduct training, but also to teach the student to think independently, solve problems in a practical way, and approach them creatively. This, in turn, means that the teacher himself must be ready to constantly learn, accept innovations and apply them in pedagogical activities.

From a socio-pedagogical point of view, the professional training of future teachers of technological education is closely related to the development of society. Because a student who is studying today can be an innovator, manufacturer, engineer, IT specialist of tomorrow. The influence of a teacher of technological education in the formation of such potential young people is incomparable. Thus, the professional training of a teacher is important not only on an individual, but also on a social scale. Also, the discussion will focus on the effective use of new tools such as digital technologies, distance learning, virtual laboratories and simulation in the educational process. A future teacher must not only know these technologies, but also have the skills to convey them to students in a simple, understandable and effective way. This in itself requires strengthening the practical approach to the educational process, an inextricable link with real production and constant updating. Therefore, based on the discussion, the following conclusion can be drawn: the professional training of future teachers of technological education is a comprehensive process that includes not only knowledge of their profession, but also the art of teaching, social responsibility, pedagogical didactics and keeping up with the times.

Conclusion.

The above analysis and discussion show that the development of professional training of future teachers of technological education is one of the integral and relevant directions of the modern educational process. Rapid changes in technological fields, the aspiration of society towards innovative development, and the need to teach the younger generation to think technically further increase the socio-pedagogical significance of this process. The process of professional training should not be limited to theoretical knowledge, but should include practical skills, a creative approach, communicative potential and the effective use of information technologies. Integrated curricula, modern methods, practical training organized in collaboration with production and close ties with the social environment play an important role in the formation of the professional competence of a future teacher. Therefore, when training teachers working in the field of technological education, pedagogical institutions should pay special attention not only to modern technologies, but also to such basic principles as humanity, social responsibility, and an educational approach. After all, every teacher being formed today is a force that creates the future.

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